

Chip Signal Analysis by Using Adaptive Short-Time Fractional Fourier Transform

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an adaptive short-time fractional Fourier transform. The proposed transform improves the resolution of the short-time Fourier transform for chirp signals, and avoids the cross-terms. The proposed adaptive short-time Fourier transform is based on the de-chirp effect of the fractional Fourier transform. It adaptively de-chirps the signal with time to achieve a high signal concentration in the time-frequency domain. An effective measure for local signal concentration is used to optimize the selection of the parameter of the fractional Fourier transform.

1 INSTRUCTION

Time-Frequency Distributions [1, 2] describe signals in terms of their joint time and frequency components. They are useful for a variety of signals, such as speech and music, which contain time-varying frequency contents. Several techniques are available to calculate such distributions. Among them, the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) and the Wigner-Ville distribution (WVD) [1, 2] are widely used.

STFT is a simple and powerful method which uses the spectrum of a segment of the signal centered at a time to represent the instant spectrum of the signal at that time. The advantages of STFT include its simplicity and easily-interpretable results. However, its poor resolution for chirp signals in the time-frequency representation is a fatal disadvantage. On the other hand, WVD has a number of desirable properties, including high signal concentration in the time-frequency domain[2], but its conspicuous drawback of producing cross-terms severely limits its applicability. The cross-terms introduced by WVD between multiple signal components in time-frequency domain make the interpretation of WVD difficult in many practical applications. Many methods [2, 3, 4] have been proposed to attenuate the cross-terms by means of a smoothing operation (i.e. low pass filtering). Unfortunately, this attenuation of interference terms comes at the cost of a loss of time-frequency concentration. In fact, it is needed to provide a high resolution time-frequency presentation for some

applications that avoids the extensive cross-terms associated with WVD and other bilinear presentation.

This paper proposes a new adaptive short-time fractional Fourier transform (ASFFT) to obtain high resolution for chirp signals without introducing cross-terms. Based on the observation that STFT achieves high concentration for constant frequency signals and poor resolution for chirp signals, the proposed transform adaptively de-chirps the signals before applying the Fourier transform. The fractional Fourier transform (FRFT) is used as the de-chirp transform. The proposed transform first chops the signal into segments with a window function, and then applies FRFT on every segment with a rotation parameter adaptively determined by the signal in the segment before the Fourier transform.

2 ADAPTIVE STFT

2.1 Short-Time Fourier Transform and its improvement

The short-time Fourier transform (STFT) is defined as

$$(\text{STFT}(f))(t, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\tau)w(\tau - t)e^{-j\omega\tau}d\tau \quad (1)$$

in which $f : R \rightarrow R$ is the signal and $w(t)$ is the window function. The STFT at time t is the Fourier transform of the signal $f(t)$ multiplied by a shifted window $w(\tau - t)$ centered around t . The STFT may also be expressed in terms of the spectra of the signal and window function,

$$(\text{STFT}(f))(t, \omega) = e^{-j\omega t} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} F(\omega')W(\omega' - \omega)e^{j\omega't}d\omega' \quad (2)$$

where $F(\omega)$ and $W(\omega)$ are the spectra of $f(t)$ and $w(t)$, respectively. It shows that STFT can also be interpreted as the inverse Fourier transform of the windowed spectrum $F(\omega')W(\omega' - \omega)$, which can be interpreted as the result of passing the signal $F(\omega')$ through a bandpass filter centered around the analysis frequency ω .

Consequently, the concentration of STFT can be improved by improving the concentration of $F(\omega)$, the spectrum of $f(t)$. For chirp signals, a de-chirp transform which translates a chirp signal into a constant frequency

signal can improve the concentration of chirp signals in time-frequency domain, since the spectrum of a constant frequency signal has a higher concentration.

Therefore an improved short-time Fourier transform (ISTFT) for chirp signals is defined as

$$\left(\text{ISTFT}(f)\right)(t, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\text{DC}(f)\right)(\tau) w(\tau - t) e^{-j\omega\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

where $\left(\text{DC}(f)\right)(\tau)$ is the de-chirp transform of $f(t)$. With the de-chirp transform, ISTFT will have a better concentration in the time-frequency domain than STFT for chirp signals.

The de-chirp operation of signal $f(t)$ in (3) should satisfy the following conditions to make sure the results of ISTFT is plausible and consistent with our intuition.

1. Energy condition

$$\int |(\text{DC}(f))(t)|^2 dt = \int |f(t)|^2 dt \quad (4)$$

This means that the de-chirp operation should preserve the energy of the input signal.

2. Center nominal frequency

The nominal frequency of a chirp signal can be defined as the derivative of its phase. For signal $f(t) = Ae^{j\phi(t)}$, where $\phi(t)$ is the phase function, its nominal frequency $\left(\text{NF}(f)\right)(t)$ is

$$\left(\text{NF}(f)\right)(t) = \phi'(t) \quad (5)$$

The center nominal frequency, defined by

$$\text{CNF}(f) = \frac{\int |f(t)|^2 \left(\text{NF}(f)\right)(t) dt}{\int |f(t)|^2 dt} \quad (6)$$

is the average of nominal frequency. The weight of each element is proportion to its power.

The center nominal frequency condition of the de-chirp transform is that the center nominal frequency should not be changed by the transform, that is

$$\text{CNF}\left(\text{DC}(f)\right) = \text{CNF}(f) \quad (7)$$

2.2 Fractional Fourier Transform and De-chirp Transform

The Fourier transform is one of the most important mathematical tools used in physical optics, theory of linear system and signal processing [6, 7]. The generalization of the Fourier transform, fractional Fourier transform (FRFT), was first introduced by Namias in 1980 [8, 9]. The FRFT has a parameter α and can be interpreted as a rotation of the input signal by an angle α in the time-frequency domain [5]. An FRFT with

$\alpha = \pi/2$ corresponds to the classical Fourier transform, and an FRFT with $\alpha = 0$ corresponds to the identity operator.

The FRFT is defined [5, 8] as

$$\left(\text{FRFT}(f)\right)(u) = F_\alpha(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) K_\alpha(t, u) dt \quad (8)$$

$$K_\alpha(t, u) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{1-j \cot \alpha}{2\pi}} e^{j \frac{t^2+u^2}{2} - jut \csc \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is not a multiple of } \pi \\ \delta(t-u) & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is a multiple of } 2\pi \\ \delta(t+u) & \text{if } \alpha + \pi \text{ is a multiple of } 2\pi \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where α is the rotation angle. Some Properties of FRFT and transforms of chirp signals are listed in Table 2 [5].

Table 1: Some Properties of FRFT and transforms of chirp signals

	Signal	Fractional FT with angle α
1	$x(t)e^{jvt}$	$X_\alpha(u - v \sin \alpha) e^{-j \frac{u^2}{2} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + juv \cos \alpha}$
2*	$e^{j \frac{c}{2} t^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{1+j \tan \alpha}{1+c \tan \alpha}} e^{j \frac{u^2}{2} \frac{c - \tan \alpha}{1+c \tan \alpha}}$

* if $\alpha - \arctan c - \frac{\pi}{2}$ is not a multiple of π .

From table 2, we can obtain that when $\tan \alpha = a$, the FRFT of chirp signal $f_s(t) = e^{j(\omega_0 + \frac{a}{2}t)t}$, $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$, is a constant frequency signal.

$$\begin{aligned} & F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1+j \tan \alpha}{1+a \tan \alpha}} e^{-j \frac{u^2}{2} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha} e^{j\omega_0 u \cos \alpha} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (10) \\ &= C \cos \alpha e^{j\omega_0 u \cos \alpha} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \end{aligned}$$

$$C = e^{j \frac{-\omega_0 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha}{2}} \quad (11)$$

The center nominal frequency of $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$ is $\omega_0 \cos \alpha$, which is not equal to ω_0 , the center nominal frequency of the original signal $f_s(t) = e^{j(\omega_0 + \frac{a}{2}t)t}$. The reason for this difference is that the rotation of the signal in time-frequency domain by FRFT extends the time axis of the signal. This weakness can be overcome by an inverse operation. To preserve the energy of the signal during the opposition operation, an adjustment of the amplitude of the signal is needed, shown in (20).

$$\int |F_{s\alpha}(u)|^2 du = \int |\sqrt{|k|} F_{s\alpha}(ku)|^2 du \quad k \text{ is a constant} \quad (12)$$

For $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$, using $u' = u \cos \alpha$ in (18) and dividing it by $\cos \alpha$, we obtain

$$F'_{s\alpha}(u')|_{\tan \alpha = a} = C e^{j\omega_0 u'} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (13)$$

whose center nominal frequency is ω_0 . So the de-chirp operation of FRFT for signal $f_s(t)$ is

$$\left(\text{FRFT}_{dc}(f_s)\right)(u) = \frac{1}{\cos \alpha} \int f(t) K_\alpha(t, \frac{u}{\cos \alpha}) dt |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (14)$$

This transform satisfies the conditions for the de-chirp transform of ISTFT, defined in (4) and (7), for FRFT preserves the energy of input signal [5], shown as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |f(t)|^2 dt = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |F_{\alpha}(u)|^2 du \quad (15)$$

The FRFT and the scale operation are used to de-chirp the signal before the Fourier transform to improve the concentration of STFT for chirp signals. The availability of fast algorithms is very important for the application of ASFFT, since FRFT carries a heavy computational load [5]. Detailed computation by using fast algorithms of DFT will be described in the full paper.

2.3 Fractional Fourier Transform and De-chirp Transform

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The FRFT is defined [5, 8] as

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{FRFT}(f))(u) &= F_{\alpha}(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t)K_{\alpha}(t, u)dt \quad (16) \\ K_{\alpha}(t, u) &= \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{1-j \cot \alpha}{2\pi}} e^{j \frac{t^2+u^2}{2} - jut \csc \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is not a multiple of } \pi \\ \delta(t-u) & \text{if } \alpha \text{ is a multiple of } 2\pi \\ \delta(t+u) & \text{if } \alpha + \pi \text{ is a multiple of } 2\pi \end{cases} \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

where α is the rotation angle. Some Properties of FRFT and transforms of chirp signals are listed in Table 2 [5].

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	Signal	Fractional Fourier transform with angle α
1	$x(t)e^{jvt}$	$X_{\alpha}(u - v \sin \alpha) e^{-j \frac{v^2}{2} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + jvu \cos \alpha}$
2*	$e^{j \frac{c}{2} t^2}$	$\sqrt{\frac{1+j \tan \alpha}{1+c \tan \alpha}} e^{j \frac{u^2}{2} \frac{c - \tan \alpha}{1+c \tan \alpha}}$

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From table 2, we can obtain that when $\tan \alpha = a$, the FRFT of chirp signal $f_s(t) = e^{j(\omega_0 + \frac{c}{2}t)t}$, $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$, is a constant frequency signal.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a} &= \sqrt{\frac{1+j \tan \alpha}{1+a \tan \alpha}} e^{-j \frac{\omega_0}{2} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha} e^{j \omega_0 u \cos \alpha} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (18) \\ &= C \cos \alpha e^{j \omega_0 u \cos \alpha} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \end{aligned}$$

$$C = e^{j \frac{\alpha - \omega_0 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha}{2}} \quad (19)$$

The center nominal frequency of $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$ is $\omega_0 \cos \alpha$, which is not equal to ω_0 , the center nominal frequency of the original signal $f_s(t) = e^{j(\omega_0 + \frac{c}{2}t)t}$. The reason for this difference is that the rotation of the signal in time-frequency domain by FRFT extends the time axis of the signal. This weakness can be overcome by an inverse operation. To preserve the energy of the signal during the opposition operation, an adjustment of the amplitude of the signal is needed, shown in (20).

$$\int |F_{s\alpha}(u)|^2 du = \int |\sqrt{|k|} F_{s\alpha}(ku)|^2 du \quad k \text{ is a constant} \quad (20)$$

For $F_{s\alpha}(u)|_{\tan \alpha = a}$, using $u' = u \cos \alpha$ in (18) and dividing it by $\cos \alpha$, we obtain

$$F'_{s\alpha}(u')|_{\tan \alpha = a} = C e^{j \omega_0 u'} |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (21)$$

whose center nominal frequency is ω_0 . So the de-chirp operation of FRFT for signal $f_s(t)$ is

$$(\text{FRFT}_{dc}(f_s))(u) = \frac{1}{\cos \alpha} \int f(t) K_{\alpha}(t, \frac{u}{\cos \alpha}) dt |_{\tan \alpha = a} \quad (22)$$

This transform satisfies the conditions for the de-chirp transform of ISTFT, defined in (4) and (7), for FRFT preserves the energy of input signal [5], shown as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |f(t)|^2 dt = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |F_{\alpha}(u)|^2 du \quad (23)$$

The FRFT and the scale operation are used to de-chirp the signal before the Fourier transform to improve the concentration of STFT for chirp signals. The availability of fast algorithms is very important for the application of ASFFT, since FRFT carries a heavy computational load [5]. Detailed computation by using fast algorithms of DFT will be described in the full paper.

3 EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

The proposed ASFFT is compared with the pseudo Wigner-Ville distribution (PWVD) [1], using a signal $f_e(t)$ consisting of two closely spaced chirps.

$$\begin{aligned} f_e(t) &= \cos\{2\pi[400(t-1)^2 + 100](t-1)\} \\ &\quad + \cos\{2\pi[400(t-1)^2 + 120](t-1)\} \quad (24) \end{aligned}$$

PWVD introduced a window function into WVD to improve the time location of WVD. Figure 1 shows the nominal center frequency distribution of $f_e(t)$, which is composed of two similar chirps. To compare with PWVD, we calculate the | ASFFT |². Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the PWVD and the | ASFFT |². These results show that the ASFFT has high concentration and no cross term interference.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed Adaptive Short-time Fractional Fourier Transform achieves high resolution and concentration in time-frequency domain for chirp signals by adaptively choosing the parameter of FRFT for each segment of the signal. The results show that the proposed ASFFT achieves the same level of concentration as PWVD without interference from the cross terms, which is a major disadvantage of PWVD. The measure of concentration is signal independent and allows the determination of the parameter of FRFT without any prior knowledge of the signal and user interaction. The effective measure of local signal concentration defined in this paper is suitable for chirp signals whose components share similar acceleration rates.

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Figure 1: Nominal center frequency distribution of signal $f_e(t)$

Figure 2: $|ASFFT|^2$ of $f_e(t)$

Figure 3: PWVD of $f_e(t)$